

The Application of Financial Accounting Standard Statements (PSAK) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research

Rodyah Awallul Rohmah, Nindi Dwi Tetria Dewi, Eka Wahyu Hestya Budianto

Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang

wahyu.ala@uin-malang.ac.id

Abstract: This study aims to determine the development of research around the application of Statement of Financial Accounting Standards (SFAS) in Islamic Financial Institutions. The research was conducted from 2007 to 2022, by searching national journals indexed by Sinta via the Garuda website, with the keyword "Statement of Financial Accounting Standards". Based on the search results, there were 113 research articles, then inputted into the VOSviewer application and analyzed descriptively through a Library Research study. The results showed that the number of publications had increased significantly every year. Furthermore, based on the results detected using the VOSviewer application, research related to the application of Statement of Financial Accounting Standards (SFAS) is divided into 5 clusters and 101 items. Meanwhile, based on the results of a Library Research study, there are 1 main themes related to the application of Statement of Financial Accounting Standards (SFAS) in Islamic Financial Institutions.

Keywords: Statement of Financial Accounting Standards (SFAS); Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Library Research; Islamic Financial Institutions

Introduction

In every company, of course several reports are required to be made at the end of each period. Financial reports are records of a company's financial information in a predetermined accounting period. This report can describe the company's financial condition and also the situation or state of the company's performance. Financial reports contain accurate recording of transactions carried out by a company during a period, including purchase and sale transactions, which results in precise calculations. Financial reports are very important for every company, because with these reports, companies can carry out analyzes to assess whether the company experienced profits or losses during a certain period, and then can make the right decisions to increase or improve the company's performance in the next period (Harahap, 2001).

The company's financial reports must be correct and up to date. Financial reports can provide a clear, reliable, relevant and comparable picture of a company's financial position to interested parties (Zanah et al., 1945). PSAK No. 101 is mandatory for organizations/institutions such as Sharia Financial Institutions which relate to the presentation and preparation of financial reports in Sharia Financial Institutions. The priority of Sharia Financial Institutions is to have financial reports that are accurate, relevant and comparable. By implementing PSAK No. 101 in Sharia Financial Institutions, Sharia Financial Institutions can manage and compile information related to financial reporting in a higher quality manner (Sutarti et al., 2012)

The application of Statements of Financial Accounting Standards (PSAK) has been widely carried out, as evidenced by the existence of many studies related to PSAK which are implemented in various institutions or companies in various regions. This shows that many companies and financial institutions, both sharia and conventional, have adapted their financial reports to PSAK. This is the right decision, because the various statements or rules contained in PSAK in each number provide benefits for the company, for example making it easier for the company to prepare

and present financial reports that are relevant, good, and can be compared by interested parties (Harahap, 2019).

Every year, scientific publications regarding PSAK continue to increase. A total of 114 studies related to PSAK have been published on the Digital Reference Guard (Garuda) website until 2021. This shows that research on PSAK is of great interest to researchers. The aim of this research is to determine a map of the development of research related to PSAK in Sharia Financial Institutions over a period of 20 years using the Vosviewer bibliometric method and Library Research studies.

Library Research

Statement of Financial Accounting Standards (PSAK) is a requirement that regulates the process or procedures for preparing financial reports reported by an authorized agency. Most PSAKs take provisions from the Accounting and Auditing Organizations for Islamic Financial Institutions (AAOIFI). These Financial Accounting Standards are a supporting factor in the development of an institution or company, because of its role important in preparing financial reports. Good financial reports reflect good companies/institutions (Harahap, 2001).

Bibliometrics is the application of mathematical and statistical techniques to books or other written materials. According to Ming-yueh Tsay, bibliometric techniques can be utilized to create a statistical representation of the flow of communication in scholarship by using references (Sezgin et al., 2022). Bibliometric tests utilize qualitative and statistical analysis to describe authorship patterns in an article, which is useful for accessing or obtaining research in the field of science (Junandi, 2018).

VOSViewer is a system or software that functions to produce maps based on network data and to display and study these maps. VOSViewer's function in short is to create maps based on network data. The second step is to visualize and explore the map. In addition, VOSViewer also offers various types of maps and visualizations, including network, overlay, and density visualizations (van Eck & Waltman, 2013).

Library Research is a systematic method for presenting and reproducing findings and ideas that have been created by researchers and practitioners for assistance, evaluation, and synthesis. A Library Research seeks to identify gaps in information regarding the subject under study to identify future directions for inquiry or research. In addition, a Library Research also aims to investigate the depth or breadth of existing research on the subject being researched and to address practical problems by understanding the results of previous research. There are several steps in writing a Library Research, including: (1) determining the theme to be evaluated; (2) find appropriate sources; (3) reading literature; (4) write reviews; And (5) linking literary works with the learning that will be carried out (Ulhaq & Rahmayanti, 2020).

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in Library Research study. The object of the research is the Statement of Financial Accounting Standards (PSAK) in Sharia Financial Institutions. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is scientific publication articles regarding Statements of Financial Accounting Standards (PSAK) originating from national and accredited journals. The source of data collection comes from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). Data analysis tools are Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, VOSviewer, and Perish software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) visiting the Garuda website and Perish software, then searching for journal titles based on the title words category with keywords " Statement of Sharia Financial Accounting Standards" and "Sharia PSAK" for the entire year period (2007-2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) map the results visualization of bibliometric networks and scientific publication trends using software VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping topics, methods, research findings, and research gaps based on Library Research studies.

Results and Discussion

1. Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding PSAK in Sharia Financial Institutions

Search results for scientific publications on PSAK in Sharia Financial Institutions from 2007 to 2022 show an increase in publications every year, especially in 2021 which reached 16 articles.

Table 1. Scientific publication data regarding PSAK by year

Year	Amount Publication	Year	Amount Publication	Year	Amount Publication
2007	1	2014	7	2019	13
2008	1	2015	9	2020	12
2009	1	2016	10	2021	16
2012	6	2017	10	2022	8
2013	3	2018	16		

Total 113

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

In Table 2, there are 9 affiliates/institutions that are most associated with the publication of research articles on PSAK in Sharia Financial Institutions. The UNTAN Faculty Accounting Scientific Studies Journal (KIAFE) is the journal publishing institution that publishes the most research results on PSAK, namely 12 articles.

Table 2. Ranking of institutions and journals that publish scientific publications regarding PSAK

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Amount Publicatio ns i
Journal of Scientific Accounting Studies, Faculty of Economics, UNTAN (KIAFE)	12
EMBA Journal: Journal of Economics, Management, Business and Research	
Accounting, Scientific Journal of Accounting Economics Students	5
Al-Amwal: Journal of Sharia Economics and Banking, Ar-Ribh: Journal	

Islamic Economics, Innovative: Journal of Economics, Management, Accounting, Digital Business and Entrepreneurship, Journal of Accounting and Economics	3
<u>PSDKU Kediri Business, Sharia Economic Journal, FEB Student Scientific Journal</u> ADDIN, ACCESS: Journal of Economics and Business, Al- Musthofa: Journal of Sharia Economics, BUSINESS ECONOMICS, TEKUN: Research Journal Accounting and Business, Journal of Accounting and Sharia Business (AKSY), e_Scientific Journal of Accounting Research, EL MUHASABA: Journal Accounting (e-Journal), JIMAT (Accounting Student Scientific Journal)	2
Undiksha, Jurnal Akrab Juara, Journal of Accounting and Finance, Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sharia Economics, Scientific Journal <u>Ranggagading (JIR), Accounting Media Journal (Mediasi)</u>	

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

In Table 3, it can be seen that of the total of 113 published research articles on PSAK in Sharia Financial Institutions on the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital), the most productive researcher is Amrie Firmansyah from the STAN State Financial Polytechnic who has written 4 journal articles.

Table 3. Productivity of researchers around PSAK

Researcher	Amount Publication
Amrie Firmansyah (STAN State Financial Polytechnic)	4
Eny Latifah (National Development University "Veteran" East Java)	3
Agusdiwana Suarni (Muhammadiyah University of Makassar), Lidia Mawikere (Sam Ratulangi University Manado), Rifqi Muhammad (Indonesian Islamic University), Aldhika Yusnar Fahmie (Indonesian Islamic University), Sriwardany	2
(Al Washliyah Archipelago Muslim University Medan) Haidir (Al Washliyah Archipelago Muslim University Medan), Eny Latifah (Tarbiyatut Tholabah Islamic Institute Lamongan), Retno Dyah Pekerti (Galuh University)	

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Bibliometric Mapping of Research Regarding PSAK in Sharia Financial Institutions

Search results on the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba), were obtained 113 research article about PSAK in Sharia Financial Institutions in Indonesia. Then the

- Cluster 5, purple consists of 13 topics, namely: activity, business person, condition, financial report, financial statement, foundation, implementation, lack, order, practice, PSAK sharia, PSAK sharia no, transaction.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Implementation of PSAK in Sharia Financial Institutions

Library Research study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 23 findings in the Library Research mapping regarding the application of PSAK to Sharia Financial Institutions (Budianto, 2023) (Gozali et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Rofika et al., 2023) (Budianto, Dewi, et al., 2023) (Budianto, Saputra, et al., 2023) (Budianto, 2022) (Budianto, 2022) (Budianto & Dewi, 2022) (Emiliani et al. al., 2023), namely:

First, the relationship between PSAK and AAOIFI and IFSB, namely: (1) Accounting and Auditing Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions/AAOIFI. In this case, AAOIFI has a financial accounting standard known as FAS (Financial Accounting Standards) which regulate financial accounting practices in Islamic financial institutions. AAOIFI FAS includes concepts specific to Islamic financial products and transactions such as mudharabah, musharakah, and sukuk. PSAK also accommodates sharia accounting principles contained in FAS AAOIFI in several of its statements. (2) International Financial Reporting Standards/IFRS. PSAK reflects the influence of IFRS in a number of its statements, because most PSAK are based on the same accounting principles as IFRS. In this case, PSAK has been adopted by Indonesia by adopting IFRS as its basis. However, there are several differences between PSAK and IFRS, especially in the areas of public sector and non-profit sector financial reporting.

Second, the application of PSAK to Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises/MSMEs in Banjarejo Panekan Village, Magetan. The application of PSAK to MSMEs aims to ensure that their financial reports are prepared to the same standards and are easily understood by interested parties, such as business owners, employees, banks and other parties who need financial information. In implementing PSAK, MSMEs must pay attention to the following things: (1) MSMEs must prepare financial reports by paying attention to generally accepted accounting principles, where the financial reports prepared must include profit and loss statements, balance sheets and cash flow reports. (2) MSMEs must use a measurement method that is in accordance with PSAK for each item in the financial statements, for example, revenue recognition must be in accordance with PSAK 23 concerning income, while recognition of costs must be in accordance with PSAK 16 concerning expenses. (3) MSMEs must provide adequate information in financial reports, such as disclosure of accounting policies used, fixed assets, debts, receivables, and so on; And (4) MSMEs must maintain consistency in using the same accounting policies from time to time, which will make it easier for parties who need financial information to compare the performance of MSMEs from year to year.

Third, the relationship between the implementation of PSAK and Islamic law. In a financial context, the application of PSAK can be related to Islamic law several things, including: (1) PSAK 23 concerning Revenue Recognition states that revenue must be recognized when it occurs, namely when a product has been delivered or a service has been provided to a customer. This is in accordance with the accounting principle known as revenue recognition. However, in Islamic law, income earned from the sale of goods or services may not always be recognized as income directly, depending on whether the transaction is sharia-compliant or not. (2) Some PSAKs, such as PSAK 105 concerning Sharia Accounting, regulate how entities can apply sharia accounting principles in their financial reporting. This is related to Islamic

law which encourages the use of sharia principles in all aspects of life, including in the world of business and finance. (3) PSAK 16 concerning Fixed Assets regulates the recognition of costs and expenses related to fixed assets. Meanwhile, Islamic law requires that every transaction must be carried out honestly, fairly and transparently. Therefore, every recognized cost and expense must be justified and adjusted to applicable accounting principles.

Fourth, the application of PSAK to the Sharia Pawn industry. Several things that need to be considered in applying PSAK to the Sharia Pawn industry are as follows: (1) In the Sharia Pawn industry, pawned assets are recognized as fixed assets or productive assets obtained through a pawn contract with certain conditions. Recognition and measurement of pledged assets must follow the applicable PSAK, but must pay attention to the characteristics of the pledge contract being entered into. (2) In the Sharia Pawn industry, costs and income must be calculated based on sharia principles, so that there is no element of usury or interest in the calculation. Costs incurred such as administrative costs, operational costs and storage costs for pawned goods must be calculated in a manner that complies with sharia principles. Income obtained from the sale of pawned goods must be calculated in a manner that complies with sharia principles. (3) Recording of pawn transactions must be done properly and correctly, so that no errors occur in transaction management. When recording transactions, it is necessary to pay attention to pawned assets, costs and income, and also compliance with sharia principles. (4) Financial reporting in the Sharia Pawn industry must comply with applicable accounting standards, and must pay attention to sharia principles. Financial reporting must include profit and loss statements, balance sheets and cash flows, and must provide sufficient and accurate information regarding the company's financial performance.

Fifth, critical Exposure Draft PSAK Syariah. Several factors that need to be considered in criticizing the Sharia PSAK Exposure Draft include: (1) Sharia accounting standards must comply with sharia principles that regulate Islamic law. Consistency between accounting standards and sharia principles must be considered. (2) Accounting standards must be in accordance with business and industry conditions. Accounting standards that are too complicated or impractical can make it difficult for companies to implement them. (3) Accounting standards must ensure transparency and openness in financial reporting. This is important so that stakeholders can understand the company's financial performance better. (4) The company must consider the possible impact on the company's finances in connection with the implementation of sharia accounting standards. Companies must ensure that these standards are in accordance with the company's financial needs and do not harm the company significantly. (5) Sharia accounting standards must be in accordance with agreed international standards. This is important so that sharia companies can compete with conventional companies globally.

Sixth, the application of PSAK to the perception of internal accountants. In terms of the application of PSAK to the perception of internal accountants, internal accountants or what are usually referred to as internal auditors need to understand and apply PSAK consistently in carrying out their duties. Several things that internal accountants need to pay attention to when implementing PSAK include: (1) Internal accountants need to understand PSAK and other applicable financial accounting standards to be able to evaluate the company's compliance with these standards; (2) In carrying out internal audits, internal accountants need to ensure that the methodology used is in accordance with PSAK standards and meets existing internal audit requirements; (3) Internal accountants need to carry out appropriate analysis and evaluation of the company's financial reports, taking into account the applicable PSAK standards, so that they can provide accurate assessments and provide useful

suggestions for improvement; And (4) Internal accountants need to ensure that they maintain ethics and integrity in carrying out internal audit duties, so that the audit results provided can be trusted and can be used as a reference in decision making.

Seventh, implementation of PSAK No. 16 on fixed asset accounting systems and procedures. This can be done with the following steps: (1) Identify Fixed Assets. The first step is to identify all fixed assets owned by the company. Fixed assets are assets owned by a company for use in the company's operations for more than one accounting period. Fixed assets include land, buildings, machines, vehicles, office equipment, and so on. (2) Measurement of Fixed Asset Value. After identifying fixed assets, the next step is to measure the value of these fixed assets. The value of fixed assets can be measured based on acquisition cost, fair value, or replacement cost. The choice of this measurement depends on the type of fixed assets owned by the company. (3) Recording of Fixed Asset Transactions. Transactions related to fixed assets must be recorded correctly and completely in journals and ledgers. These records include recording expenditures to acquire, increase, or repair fixed assets. (4) Arrangement of Fixed Asset Depreciation. Fixed assets have a limited useful life, so depreciation must be calculated to recognize their use over their useful life. Depreciation must be calculated using an appropriate method, such as the straight-line method or the sum of the years digits method. (5) Control of Fixed Assets. Control of fixed assets must be carried out to prevent misuse, loss or damage. These steps include regularly recording and monitoring fixed assets, tracking usage and maintenance, and renewing insurance or installing security equipment. (6) Financial Reporting. Information about fixed assets must be reported in the financial statements. This reporting includes notes on fixed asset accounting policies, details of fixed asset values, recognized depreciation, and additional information.

Eighth, implementation of PSAK No. 27 regarding recognition of income and expenses at KSP Syariah Al-Ikhlas Takalar Regency. The following are several important points in implementing PSAK No. 27: (1) Revenue must be recognized when there is an event that causes the income to occur and the amount of the income can be measured reliably, in which case the revenue must be measured by the fair value of the consideration received or to be received; (2) Expenses must be recognized when there is an event that causes the expense to occur and the amount of the expense can be measured reliably, in which case the expense must be measured at the fair value of the benefits issued or to be issued; (3) PSAK No. 27 stipulates that there are several revenue recognition methods, namely the percentage completion method, the revenue recognition method based on project completion, the revenue recognition method based on the completion of a stage, the revenue recognition method based on delivery, and the revenue recognition method based on usage; (4) PSAK No. 27 also stipulates that there are several expense recognition methods, namely the expense recognition method based on outflows, the expense recognition method based on project completion, and the time-based expense recognition method; and (5) In addition, PSAK No. 27 also regulates the disclosure of information that must be submitted in financial reports related to income and expenses, such as the amount of income and expenses, methods for recognizing income and expenses, as well as information related to the measurement and recognition of income and expenses.

Ninth, implementation of PSAK No. 59 regarding: (1) Recognition and measurement of Funding products at BMT in Yogyakarta, namely: (a) Mudharabah Products: Profits and losses from Mudharabah products are recognized and measured at maturity. The portion of profits that is the right of the bank is recognized as Bank Business Income, while the portion that is the right of the customer is recognized as Profit Sharing Income. (b) Musyarakah Products: Gains and losses from Musyarakah products are recognized and measured at maturity. The portion of profits that is the right of the bank is recognized as Bank Business Income, while

the portion that is the right of the customer is recognized as Profit Sharing Income.

(c) Murabahah Products: Costs for procuring goods and services incurred by the bank are recognized as expenses at the time of the transaction. Gains are recognized and measured at maturity.

(d) Ijarah Products: The cost of acquiring the asset or item being leased is recognized as an expense at the time of the transaction. Income from ijarah is recognized over the rental period.

(e) Wadiah Products: Costs incurred in managing Wadiah products are recognized as expenses. There is no revenue recognition in Wadiah products. Cash Flow movements are based on the sharia accounting system. Several sharia accounting principles that are relevant in implementing PSAK No. 59 include:

(a) Principle of justice and equality: This principle emphasizes that in carrying out financial transactions, all parties must be treated fairly and equally. In this case, the application of PSAK No. 59 must pay attention to the rights of shareholders and investors and ensure that the cash flow statement reflects actual cash movements.

(b) Transparency principle: This principle emphasizes that financial reports must be transparent and clear so as to enable users of financial reports to understand clearly and objectively the company's financial condition. In this case, the cash flow report presented must be easy to understand and contain fairly complete information regarding cash movements.

(c) Principle of responsibility: This principle emphasizes that an entity must be responsible for the financial transactions carried out. In this case, the application of PSAK No. 59 must ensure that cash movements are recorded accurately and thoroughly, and avoid accounting practices that are detrimental or create unnecessary risks. In implementing PSAK No. 59 in the sharia accounting system, it is also necessary pay attention to the following things:

(a) In the sharia accounting system, there is a separation between halal funds and haram funds. Therefore, cash movements from halal funds and haram funds must be recorded separately and clearly, and reported in separate cash flow statements.

(b) In carrying out financial transactions, entities must comply with sharia principles, such as the principles of justice, not usury, not accepting or giving unauthorized gifts, and so on. Therefore, the cash flow report must reflect financial transactions that comply with sharia principles.

(c) In the sharia accounting system, there are financial instruments that comply with sharia principles, such as mudharabah, musyarakah, murabahah, and so on. Therefore, cash movements from sharia financial instruments must be recorded separately and clearly, and reported in a separate cash flow statement.

(3) Qardhul Hasan Financing at BMT Al-Ittihad Rumbai Pekanbaru, Bank Muamalat Jember, namely:

(a) Recognition: Receipt of Qardhul Hasan Financing must be recognized when received and recorded as a debt. Meanwhile, for the party providing the loan, it is not recognized as income or profit.

(b) Measurement: Qardhul Hasan financing is not subject to interest or compensation. Therefore, there are no costs associated with this financing.

(c) Reporting: In the financial statements, Qardhul Hasan Financing is reported as debt and listed in the short-term or long-term liabilities section depending on the repayment period. In the notes to the financial report, it is best to state the amount of financing received, the repayment period, and other conditions.

(d) Disclosure: Disclosures related to Qardhul Hasan Financing must include information regarding the amount of financing received, repayment period, conditions related to the financing, as well as the accounting policies applied.

Mudharabah financing compliance with sharia aspects of fiqh Shafi'iyah. Several aspects of Syafi'iyah Islamic jurisprudence that must be considered in implementing PSAK No. 59 are as follows:

(a) The law of mudharabah: According to Syafi'iyah jurisprudence, mudharabah is a cooperative agreement between shahibul maal and mudharib which involves sharing profits and losses. In implementing PSAK No. 59, it is necessary to consider the mudharabah law adopted by Shafi'iyah jurisprudence to ensure that financing is carried out in accordance with Islamic sharia principles.

(b) Profit sharing: According to Shafi'iyah

jurisprudence, the distribution of profits in a mudharabah must be agreed upon before the contract is executed. In implementing PSAK No. 59, it is necessary to consider these rules to determine how the distribution of profits should be carried out in an accounting manner. (c) Financing term: According to Syafi'iyah jurisprudence, the financing term in mudharabah must be agreed upon before the contract is executed. In implementing PSAK No. 59, it is necessary to consider these rules to determine the financing period in accordance with Islamic sharia principles. (d) Use of funds: According to Syafi'iyah jurisprudence, the use of funds in mudharabah must be clear and not conflict with the principles of Islamic sharia. In implementing PSAK No. 59, it is necessary to consider the use of funds in accordance with Islamic sharia principles.

Tenth, implementation of PSAK No. 69 regarding critical biological assets from a sharia perspective. Several things need to be considered in implementing PSAK No. 69 from a sharia perspective, among others: (1) Recognition of biological assets must be carried out in a fair and careful manner, taking into account economic feasibility and sharia feasibility; (2) Measurement of the value of biological assets must be carried out objectively and based on actual facts. This measurement should reflect the true value of the biological asset; (3) The presentation of biological assets must be carried out clearly and transparently, so as to provide complete and accurate information regarding the company's financial position; and (4) When selling biological assets, the company must pay attention to the conditions stipulated in sharia, such as fair buying and selling conditions and other conditions that are in accordance with sharia principles.

Eleventh, implementation of PSAK No. 71 at BTN Syariah KC Malang. Several important points in implementing PSAK No. 71 in sharia banking, including: (1) Valuation of financial instruments based on sharia principles. Sharia banking must assess the financial instruments it owns based on sharia principles. This aims to ensure that these financial instruments comply with sharia principles such as fairness, sustainability and compliance with applicable laws and regulations. (2) Income recognition based on sharia principles. Revenue recognition in sharia banking must be carried out based on sharia principles, such as profit sharing or nisbah. This is different from conventional banks which usually use an interest system. (3) Transparent disclosure of information. Sharia banking must disclose transparent information related to the financial instruments it owns. This aims to provide clarity and confidence to customers and investors regarding the financial performance of sharia banks. (4) Financial reporting in accordance with sharia principles. Sharia banking must present financial reports that comply with sharia principles, such as financial reports based on sharia contracts or agreements used in financial instruments.

Twelfth, implementation of PSAK No. 101 about: (1) Presentation of Financial Reports at Bank Jabar Banten Syariah, Kopontren Al-Barkah Wonodadi Blitar, BMT Nurul Islam Batam, BMT Al-Ittihad Pekanbaru. PSAK No. 101 has several special requirements that apply to banks, including: (a) Banks must present a statement of financial position with a grouping of assets, liabilities and equity based on liquidity; (b) Banks must provide additional information regarding credit risk, market risk, liquidity risk and operational risk; (c) Banks must present cash flow reports in three parts, namely cash flows from operating activities, cash flows from investing activities, and cash flows from financing activities; and (d) Banks must present information regarding the fair value of financial instruments and the effect of changes in fair value in the financial statements. (2) The level of student understanding of the application of this PSAK. The level of student understanding of the application of PSAK No. 101 may vary depending on their education level and academic background. However, in general, accounting students should have a good

understanding of generally accepted accounting principles, including PSAK No. 101 concerning Presentation of Financial Statements. To deepen understanding of the application of PSAK No. 101, students can take several steps, such as reading related book texts and journals, attending lectures and discussions in class, and attending related training and seminars. Apart from that, students can also deepen their understanding by doing direct practice at companies or financial institutions that implement PSAK No. 101 in presenting its financial statements.

Thirteenth, implementation of PSAK No. 102 about:

(1) Accounting treatment of Mudharabah/profit sharing agreements at Bank Syariah Mandiri KC Makassar, Bank Muamalat KC Pekanbaru. A Mudharabah contract is a type of contract in sharia banking which is entered into between the capital owner (shahibul maal) and the capital manager (mudharib). In this contract, profits or business results are divided based on a previously agreed ratio. PSAK No. 102 stipulates that in sharia accounting, capital owners (shahibul maal) must record mudharabah contracts as investments on the balance sheet, while capital managers (mudharib) must record mudharabah contracts as debt on the balance sheet. When profits are divided, capital owners must record profits as income in the profit and loss statement, while capital managers must record profits as expenses in the profit and loss statement.

(2) Accounting treatment of Murabahah contracts at Islamic Microfinance Institutions, BNI Syariah KC Katamso, BNI Syariah KC Makassar, BRI Syariah KC Tanjung Karang Lampung, Bank Syariah Mandiri KC Depok, Bank Syariah Mandiri KC Manado, Sharia Microfinance Institution in Aceh Besar, Bank Sumsel Babel Syariah KC Lubuklinggau, BMT Al-Ittihad Cikurukuk Tasikmalaya, KSPPS BMT Lumbung Artho Jepara, KSPPS BMT NU Jombang, Bank East Java Syariah KC Malang, BRI Syariah KC Bululawang Malang, BMT Maslahah Sidogiri, BMT in Pati Regency, Bank Sulselbar Syariah KC Makassar, BMT Ummah Bajarmasin. A Murabahah contract is a type of contract in sharia banking that is entered into between a buyer and a seller. In this contract, the buyer buys an item from the seller at a previously agreed price, then the item is resold by the buyer to the seller at a higher price on credit. PSAK No. 102 stipulates that in sharia accounting, sharia banks must record murabahah contracts as receivables on the balance sheet. At the time of repayment, Islamic banks must record the repayment as income in the profit and loss statement.

(3) Accounting treatment of Murabahah contracts in mortgage financing at BTN Syariah KC Surabaya. In sharia mortgage financing, sharia banks buy houses from developers and resell them to customers at a higher price using credit. PSAK No. 102 stipulates that in sharia accounting, sharia banks must record mortgage financing as receivables on the balance sheet. At the time of repayment, Islamic banks must record the repayment as income in the profit and loss statement. Apart from that, Islamic banks must also record costs related to mortgage financing, such as notary fees and administration fees, as costs in the profit and loss statement.

Fourteenth, implementation of PSAK No. 103 regarding Wakalah and Salam contracts in E-Commerce transactions. A wakalah contract is an agreement in which one party (muklik) is given trust by another party (muwakkil) to carry out certain actions or transactions. In e-commerce transactions, wakalah contracts can be used to facilitate transactions between sellers and buyers. For example, the seller can appoint an agent as the agent to send the product to the buyer. The agent will then receive compensation from the seller for his services as a representative. In its application, PSAK No. 103 requires an agreement between the parties involved regarding the duties, responsibilities and compensation received by the deputy. Apart from that, supporting documents such as receipts, notes or proof of delivery must be maintained as proof of the transaction that occurred. A salam contract is a

contract in which the seller delivers goods at a certain time, while payments are made at a future date. In e-commerce transactions, greeting contracts can be used to facilitate transactions between seller and buyer. In its application, PSAK No. 103 requires an agreement regarding the price, time and place of delivery of goods, as well as payment. Apart from that, supporting documents such as invoices or travel documents must be maintained as proof of the transactions that occurred.

Fifteenth, implementation of PSAK No. 104 about:

(1) Accounting treatment of Mudharabah/profit sharing agreements at Bank Syariah Indonesia/BSI, Savings and Loans Cooperative/KSP Syariah. The following are several important points related to the implementation of PSAK No. 104 on mudharabah/profit sharing agreements at Sharia Banks: (a) Determination of profit sharing ratio: Sharia banks must determine a profit sharing ratio that is mutually agreed between the bank and the customer. This ratio must be based on a reasonable agreement and based on actual business performance. (b) Transaction recording: Islamic banks must record every mudharabah/profit sharing transaction in their accounting clearly and separately from conventional accounting. In addition, Islamic banks must record the portion they receive from profits in their accounting as income, while the portion received by customers is recorded as expenses. (c) Financial reports: Islamic banks must present financial reports that reflect their business performance, including profit and loss statements and balance sheets. In the profit and loss statement, Islamic banks must present the portion they receive from profits as income, while the portion received by customers is recorded as expenses. Apart from that, sharia banks must also present information about the agreed profit sharing ratio and how sharia banks treat profits and losses from mudharabah/profit sharing transactions. (d) Disclosure of information: Islamic banks must disclose information about mudharabah/profit sharing transactions in the notes to their financial reports. Information that must be disclosed includes the profit sharing ratio, the amount of profit or loss obtained, as well as risk management policies related to mudharabah/profit sharing transactions.

(2) Istishna' contract in online buying and selling transactions. The following are several important points related to the implementation of PSAK No. 104 on Istishna' contracts in online buying and selling transactions: (a) Transaction identification: Sharia banks must identify transactions that use Istishna' contracts in their accounting records. Islamic banks must ensure that the transaction meets the necessary conditions, such as product or service quality criteria that must be met. (b) Transaction recording: Islamic banks must record every Istishna' transaction in their accounting clearly and separately from conventional accounting. Additionally, Islamic banks must record the costs of producing or providing goods or services as an expense in their accounting, as well as treating payments received from customers as income in their accounting. (c) Financial reports: Islamic banks must present financial reports that reflect their business performance, including profit and loss statements and balance sheets. In the profit and loss report, Islamic banks must present the income received from customers as a result of selling products or services, while the costs of producing or providing goods or services are recorded as expenses. Apart from that, Islamic banks must also present information about the Istishna' transactions carried out, including the amount of sales, production costs, and the resulting profit or loss. (d) Disclosure of information: Islamic banks must disclose information about Istishna' transactions in the notes to the financial statements they. Information that must be disclosed includes product or service quality criteria that must be met, costs of producing or providing goods or services, and risk management policies related to Istishna' transactions. In addition, Islamic banks must provide information about dispute resolution procedures that may arise in Istishna' transactions.

Sixteenth, implementation of PSAK No. 105 regarding: (1) Accounting treatment of Musyarakah contracts at Bank Syariah Indonesia KCP Subang. The following are several things that need to be considered when implementing PSAK No. 105 for Musyarakah contracts: The distribution of profits and losses must be agreed upon by all parties involved in the Musyarakah contract; Capital paid in by each party must be recorded in the accounting books as part of equity; Every transaction related to the Musyarakah contract must be recorded clearly in the accounting book; Costs incurred by each party must be recorded and charged according to their respective percentage of capital ownership. (2) Accounting treatment of Mudharabah contracts at Bank Syariah Mandiri KC Jember, BMT UGT Sidogiri Yosowilangun, Sharia Cooperative in Aceh Besar, BNI Syariah KCU Makassar, Bank Sulselbar KC Syariah Makassar, KSPPS BMT NU Jombang, BNI Syariah KC Mikro Parepare/Cirebon City, Sharia State Savings Bank KC Pekanbaru, Lamongan Sharia Cooperative, Bank Muamalat KC Pekanbaru. The following are several things that need to be considered when implementing PSAK No. 105 for Mudharabah contracts: Capital paid in by shahibul maal must be recorded in the accounting book as part of equity; Profits resulting from capital management must be shared according to the percentage agreed by both parties; Every transaction related to the Mudharabah contract must be recorded clearly in the accounting book; The costs incurred by the mudharib must be recorded and charged to the shahibul maal's capital.

Seventeenth, implementation of PSAK No. 106 regarding the accounting treatment of Musyarakah financing at BNI Syariah KC Medan, Bank Mega Syariah, Bank Syariah Mandiri KC Manado. Implementation of PSAK No. 106 in musyarakah financing is carried out in the following manner: (1) Recording Musyarakah Financing: Musyarakah financing is recorded in the musyarakah financing account ledger. When recording, you are required to record the amount of capital of each party involved in musyarakah financing. (2) Determination of Profit or Loss Share: After the project or business is completed, the profit or loss obtained from musyarakah financing must be calculated. In this case, PSAK No. 106 regulates that each party involved in musyarakah financing will receive a share of profits or losses in accordance with the initial agreement. (3) Recording of Share of Profit or Loss: After the calculation of profit or loss is complete, the share of profit or loss must be recorded for each party involved in musyarakah financing. (4) Financial Reporting: After recording the profit or loss portion, financial reporting must be carried out. The financial report must include information about musyarakah financing, the share of capital of each party, as well as the share of profit or loss obtained by each party.

Eighteenth, implementation of PSAK No. 107 about:

(1) Accounting treatment of Ijarah contracts at BNI Syariah, KSPP Syariah BMT Arma, Pegadaian Syariah Hasanuddin Branch, BRI Syariah KC Lhokseumawe. An Ijarah agreement is a rental agreement which is one of the sharia financial instruments commonly used by sharia companies in their operational activities. In PSAK No. 107, the Ijarah contract must be recognized as an asset by the lessor and is recognized as a liability by the lessor. For the lessee, Ijarah assets must be recorded in the financial statements as productive assets that can generate cash. In addition, the lessor must recognize income from rentals as income proportionally during the rental period. Meanwhile, for the renting party, the Ijarah liability must be recorded in the financial report as an obligation that must be paid. Apart from that, the renting party must also recognize the expense of the rent proportionally during the rental period.

(2) Accounting for Rahn/Gold pawn contracts at Pegadaian Syariah Simpang Patal Branch Palembang/Ujung Bulu/Jombang/Landung Sari Malang/Surabaya, Bank Syariah Mandiri KC Surabaya/Manado/Banda Aceh/Jember, Bank Jabar Banten/BJB Syariah. The Rahn or Gold Pawn Agreement

is a pawn contract which is one of the sharia financial instruments commonly used by sharia companies in their operational activities. In PSAK No. 107, the Rahn/Gold Pawn contract must be recorded in the financial statements as an asset or liability, depending on the position taken by the party entering into the Gold Pawn/Rahn contract. If the party entering into the Rahn/Gold Pawn contract is the party lending the funds, then the Rahn/Gold Pawn contract must be recorded in the financial statements as a productive asset that can generate cash. In addition, the party lending the funds must recognize income from the Rahn/Gold Pawn contract as income proportionally during the contract period. Meanwhile, if the party entering into the Rahn/Gold Pawn contract is the party borrowing the funds, then the Rahn/Gold Pawn contract must be recorded in the financial report as a liability that must be paid. In addition, the party borrowing funds must recognize the burden of the Rahn/Gold Pawn contract as interest expense proportionally during the contract period.

Nineteenth, implementation of PSAK No. 108 around

(1) Accounting for Sharia Insurance transactions using the Wakalah Bil Ujrah contract at Bumiputera Muda Syariah Serang Branch, General Takaful Insurance, AJB Bumiputera 1912 Jakarta Sharia Region, Jasindo Syariah Insurance, Family Takaful Insurance. The following is the application of PSAK No. 108 in accounting for sharia insurance transactions using the Wakalah Bil Ujrah contract: (a) Recording of sharia insurance transactions using the Wakalah Bil Ujrah contract must be carried out by separating premiums and sharia funds; (b) Premiums must be recorded as income of the sharia insurance company. Meanwhile, sharia funds must be recorded as liabilities that must be managed and invested by the sharia insurance company; (c) Sharia insurance companies must take into account operational costs and profits in the Wakalah Bil Ujrah contract; (d) The profits generated must be shared between the policy holder and the sharia insurance company in accordance with a predetermined agreement; and (e) Sharia insurance companies must present financial reports that include information about premium income, sharia funds, operational costs, profits, and profit sharing between policy holders and sharia insurance companies.

(2) Unit Linked Products against Going Concern Assumptions in Sharia Insurance Companies. In implementing PSAK No. 108, sharia insurance companies must provide adequate information about going concern assumptions and risks related to their business operations. This is important to provide certainty to customers and other interested parties about the company's ability to continue operating in the future and to carry out their obligations to customers. Apart from that, sharia insurance companies must ensure that the unit linked products they offer are in accordance with their going concern assumptions. This can be done by managing investment risks well and regularly monitoring their investment performance. Companies must also consider credit risk and market risk in determining going concern assumptions and assessing whether their unit linked products are still in line with the risks that the company can tolerate. In this regard, sharia insurance companies must adopt a sustainable approach to managing risk and ensure that their going concern assumptions remain relevant and appropriate to changing market and financial conditions in the future. Thus, the application of PSAK No. 108 in the context of unit linked products in sharia insurance companies can help increase transparency and trust in customers and other interested parties in the company's business.

(3) Compliance with the Koran, Hadith, DSN-MUI Fatwa. Several things need to be considered in implementing PSAK No. 108 which is in accordance with the Al-Quran, Hadith, and DSN-MUI Fatwa are as follows: (a) Determination of

Zakat: In the Al-Quran, Hadith, and DSN-MUI Fatwa, there are provisions that regulate who is obliged to pay zakat and how to calculate it. zakat to be paid. In implementing PSAK No. 108, it is necessary to pay attention to these provisions so that zakat is calculated and paid in accordance with Islamic teachings. (b) Zakat Management: Al-Quran, Hadith and DSN-MUI Fatwa also provide instructions regarding zakat management. In implementing PSAK No. 108, it is necessary to pay attention to these provisions to ensure that zakat management is carried out transparently and in accordance with sharia principles. (c) Zakat Reporting: PSAK No. 108 also regulates zakat reporting. In its implementation, it is necessary to pay attention to the provisions contained in the Koran, Hadith and DSN-MUI Fatwa regarding zakat reporting so that the reports presented are in accordance with sharia accounting principles.

Twentieth, implementation of PSAK No. 109 regarding:

(1) Zakat, Infaq and Alms Management Organization in Baitul Mal, Banda Aceh City. Several applications of PSAK No. 109 that must be carried out by zakat, infaq and alms management organizations include: (a) Transparent and accountable financial recording and reporting, including disclosure of information related to the receipt, use and balance of zakat, infaq and alms funds; (b) Recognition of zakat, infaq and alms income in accordance with generally accepted accounting principles and accounting standards applicable in Indonesia; (c) Preparation of financial reports accompanied by notes to the financial reports explaining the details of the management of zakat, infaq and alms funds; (d) Separation of zakat, infaq and alms funds from other funds owned by the organization, as well as the use of zakat, infaq and alms funds only for specified purposes; and (e) Strict supervision and control over the management of zakat, infaq and alms funds, including the implementation of internal and external audit mechanisms to ensure the integrity and accuracy of financial reports.

(2) Buleleng Regency BAZNAS financial report. The following are several applications of PSAK No. 109 relating to BAZNAS financial statements: (a) ZIS income must be recognized when the transaction occurs. BAZNAS must record ZIS income received, both in the form of cash and in the form of productive assets, such as property or investments. ZIS income must also be recognized in the BAZNAS financial statements clearly and separately from other sources of income. (b) BAZNAS must measure the ZIS funds managed in an appropriate manner. ZIS funds must be measured at fair value upon recognition and must be recorded separately from other assets and liabilities. PSAK No. 109 also regulates the use of ZIS funds, where ZIS funds must be used for the specified purposes. (c) BAZNAS financial reports must include information about the management of ZIS funds, including the amount of ZIS funds received, used and remaining. BAZNAS financial reports must also include information about programs and activities funded by ZIS funds. (d) BAZNAS must carry out adequate internal supervision and control to ensure that the management of ZIS funds is carried out correctly and in accordance with applicable regulations. BAZNAS must also carry out an audit of its financial reports by an independent auditor who has adequate competence and independence.

(3) Financial reports of Sharia Non-Profit Institutions. The following are several applications of PSAK No. 109 relating to the financial statements of Sharia Non-Profit Institutions: (a) Recognition of ZIS Income: Sharia Non-Profit Institutions must recognize ZIS income when the transaction occurs. ZIS income received in the form of cash or productive assets, such as property or investments, must be recorded separately and recognized in the financial statements of Sharia Non-Profit Institutions. In addition, recognition of ZIS income must be done clearly and separately from other sources of income. (b) Measurement of ZIS Funds: Sharia Non-Profit Institutions must recognize ZIS income when the transaction occurs. ZIS

income received in the form of cash or productive assets, such as property or investments, must be recorded separately and recognized in the financial statements of Sharia Non-Profit Institutions. In addition, recognition of ZIS income must be done clearly and separately from other sources of income. (c) Information Disclosure: Financial reports of Sharia Non-Profit Institutions must include information about the management of ZIS funds, including the amount of ZIS funds received, used and remaining. Financial reports must also include information about programs and activities funded by ZIS funds as well as the overall financial and operational performance of Sharia Non-Profit Institutions. Disclosure of this information must be transparent and understandable by stakeholders. (d) Audit and Supervision: Sharia Non-Profit Institutions must carry out adequate internal supervision and control to ensure that the management of ZIS funds is carried out correctly and in accordance with applicable regulations. Sharia Non-Profit Institutions must also audit their financial reports by independent auditors who have adequate competence and independence.

Twenty-first, implementation of PSAK No. 110 regarding the value of Ijarah Sukuk on the Sharia Capital Market. The following are several important things that must be considered when implementing PSAK No. 110: (1) Recognition of ijarah sukuk: Companies must recognize ijarah sukuk as debt or equity, depending on the structure of the ijarah sukuk issued. If the ijarah sukuk is issued as debt, the company must recognize the ijarah sukuk as a liability on the balance sheet. If the ijarah sukuk is issued as equity, the company must recognize the ijarah sukuk as equity in its financial statements. (2) Valuation of ijarah sukuk: Ijarah sukuk must be valued at fair value at each financial reporting date company. This assessment must be carried out by considering the business feasibility of the issuer of the sukuk ijarah, market conditions, and other factors that may affect the value of the sukuk ijarah. (3) Disclosure: Companies must provide adequate disclosure about the sukuk ijarah issued, including the structure of the sukuk ijarah, the costs associated with the issuance of the sukuk ijarah, the conditions associated with the issuance of the sukuk ijarah, and the risks associated with investing in the sukuk ijarah. (4) Management of sukuk ijarah: Companies must manage sukuk ijarah effectively, including in terms of managing funds received from sharia investors, and payments that must be made to investors in accordance with the issued sukuk ijarah agreement.

Twenty-second, implementation of PSAK No. 111 regarding Wa'd accounting in Murabahah financing contracts. Implementation of PSAK No. 111 in the Murabahah financing contract will include: (1) Recognition of Wa'd as a liability or receivable on the balance sheet, depending on the nature of the Wa'd. If the Wa'd is an agreement to receive payment in the future, then the Wa'd is recognized as a receivable. However, if the Wa'd is an agreement to pay in the future, then the Wa'd is recognized as a liability. (2) Wa'd measurement uses fair value: Fair value is the price that will be received or paid when the goods are delivered or payment is made. (3) Presentation of Wa'd in financial statements: Wa'd recognized as a liability is displayed in the liabilities section of the balance sheet, while Wa'd recognized as a receivable is displayed in the receivables section of the balance sheet.

Twenty-third, implementation of PSAK No. 112 regarding:

(1) Management of cash waqf in Sharia Cooperatives. For the implementation of PSAK No. 112 in sharia cooperatives, several things that need to be considered include: (a) Measuring cash waqf received by sharia cooperatives must be done carefully and accurately. This measurement includes measuring the value of cash waqf at the time of receipt as well as measuring the revaluation of cash waqf at the end of the reporting period. (b) Recording of cash waqf must be done separately

from other financial accounts, so as to allow for separate reporting and better supervision. (c) Sharia cooperative financial reporting must contain information related to cash waqf management, such as the amount of cash waqf received, the amount of revaluation of cash waqf at the end of the reporting period, and the use of cash waqf funds. (d) Sharia cooperatives must manage cash waqf funds carefully and responsibly. Cash waqf funds may only be used in accordance with the purpose of the waqf, such as for education, health and other social activities. (e) Sharia cooperatives must ensure that the use of cash waqf funds is carried out in a halal manner and in accordance with sharia principles.

(2) Waqf accounting, preparing financial reports for nazhir at the Indonesian Waqf Board/BWI Representative of South Kalimantan Province. This means implementing transparent and responsible financial reports, as well as consistent financial reporting components. A good and easy to understand report can provide additional information for the public, so that the public does not doubt the credibility of nazhir in waqf institutions related to the successful influence of the National Cash Waqf Movement (GNWU) established by the President.

Conclusions and recommendations

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows:

- The number of research publications regarding the application of Statements of Financial Accounting Standards (PSAK) during the period 2007 to 2022 shows a significant increase from year to year. The total number of publications is 113 research articles, which come from national journals indexed by Sinta.
- The affiliate/institution that publishes the most research results is the Journal of Accounting Scientific Studies, UNTAN Faculty (KIAFE), which is the journal publishing institution that publishes the most research results on PSAK, namely 12 articles.
- The most productive researcher in publishing research results is Amrie Firmansyah from the STAN State Finance Polytechnic who has written 4 journal articles
- In the mapping visualization using VOSviewer, research developments surrounding the application of the Statement of Financial Accounting Standards (PSAK) are divided into 5 clusters and 101 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 30 topics, cluster 2 consists of 26 topics, cluster 3 consists of 17 topics, cluster 4 consists of 15 topics, and cluster 5 consists of 13 topics.
- Based on the Library Research, there is 1 main research theme, namely the application of the Statement of Financial Accounting Standards (PSAK) to Sharia Financial Institutions.

It is recommended that further research use a larger data sample, so that it can explain a broader research mapping, considering the limitations of the data sample in this study and can add a longer research data time span so that the following research results can be obtained:

- It is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization.
- the Library Research study can be explained in a more complex way.

References

- Baranuri, M. Y., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Ijarah pada Industri Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038971>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). *Pemetaan Penelitian Akad Mudharabah Pada Lembaga*

- Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Library Research. *J-EBIS (Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Bisnis Islam)*, 7(1), 43–68. <https://doi.org/10.32505/jebis.v7i1.3895>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Akad Musyarakah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *JESI (Jurnal Ekonomi Syariah Indonesia)*, 12(1), 25–36. [https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12\(1\).25-36](https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12(1).25-36)
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Bibliometric And Library Research Of Financing Risk In Islamic Banking. *JPS (Jurnal Perbankan Syariah)*, 4(1), 79–97. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.46367/jps.v4i1.1031>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RISIKO REPUTASI PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY RESEARCH. *Al-Masraf: Jurnal Lembaga Keuangan Dan Perbankan*, 8(1), 94–113. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.15548/al-masraf.v8i1.425>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Risiko Kredit pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *BANCO: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 5(1), 20–34. <https://doi.org/10.35905/banco.v5i1.4987>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). RESEARCH MAPPING ON CREDIT RISK IN ISLAMIC AND CONVENTIONAL BANKING. *AL-INFAQ: Jurnal Ekonomi Islam*, 14(1), 73–86. <https://doi.org/10.32507/ajei.v14i1.1862>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2022). Research Mapping of Musyarakah Contracts in Islamic Financial Institutions: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research. *Maliki Islamic Economics Journal*, 2(2), 76–94. <https://doi.org/10.18860/miec.v2i2.17199>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Ju'alah pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10040276>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Sharf pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042641>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Biaya Operasional terhadap Pendapatan Operasional (BOPO) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *JAF (Journal of Accounting and Finance)*, 7(1), 34–48. <https://doi.org/10.25124/jaf.v7i1.5995>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037417>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037141>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Per Share (DPS) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *Al-Mal: Jurnal Akuntansi Dan Keuangan Islam*, 4(1), 109–126. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.24042/al-mal.v4i01.16760>

- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Economic Value Added (EVA) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037270>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Financial Value Added (FVA) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *BJRM (Bongaya Journal of Research in Management)*, 6(2), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.37888/bjrm.v6i2>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Net Operating Margin (NOM) pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *Ecobankers: Journal of Economy and Banking*, 4(2), 84–94. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8323115>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Net Profit Margin (NPM) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037209>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO NON PERFORMING FINANCING (NPF) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY RESEARCH*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038983>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO RETURN ON INVESTMENT (ROI) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY RESEARCH*. *Kompetensi (Competence : Journal of Management Studies)*, 17(1), 66–82. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.21107/kompetensi.v17i1.20002>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO WORKING CAPITAL TURNOVER (WCT) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY RESEARCH*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037081>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar cash ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037415>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037413>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar current ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037359>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar pengaruh variabel mikroekonomi: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037254>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar quick ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038973>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pengaruh Book Value per Share (BVS) pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *Islamic Economics and Business Review*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185250>

- Budianto, E. W. H., Dewi, N. D. T., & Abidin, U. A. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dana Pihak Ketiga (DPK) Pada Perbankan Syariah Dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Library Research. *Syiar Iqtishadi: Journal of Islamic Economics, Finance and Banking*, 7(1), 25–44. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.35448/jiec.v7i1.19887>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Saputra, H. M. G. A., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Koperasi Jasa Keuangan Syariah (KJKS): Studi Bibliometrik VOS viewer dan Library Research. *EL MUDHORIB: Jurnal Kajian Ekonomi Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 3(2), 131–148. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185180>
- Dewi, N. D. T., Ibad, N. N., Pratopo, G., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Manajemen Zakat Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer Dan Library Research. *Jurnal Ekonomika Dan Bisnis Islam*, 6(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.26740/jekobi.v6n1.p1-20>
- Febrian, J., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). THE EFFECT OF KNOWLEDGE, TRUST, PRODUCTS, SERVICES AND RELIGIOSITY ON INTEREST IN SAVING. *International Conference of Islamic Economics and Business 9th*, 85–96. <http://repository.uin-malang.ac.id/15487/>
- Gozali, M., Saputra, M. A., Dewi, N. D. T., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN SEPUTAR VARIABEL DETERMINAN RETURN ON EQUITY (ROE) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY RESEARCH. *IDEI: Jurnal Ekonomi & Bisnis*, 4(1), 34–47. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.38076/ideijeb.v4i1.151>
- Mawardi, M. I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Tabungan Pensiunan Nasional (BTPN) Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049566>
- Putri, S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Bukopin Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049572>
- Qudratullah, M. Q., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Murabahah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038979>
- Rahmawati, L., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar Bank Tabungan Negara (BTN) syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037422>
- Ratnasari, A. D., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Rahn (Gadai) pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038977>
- Rofiah, A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Wadiah pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042647>
- Rofika, H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN SEPUTAR MAYBANK SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY RESEARCH. *Jurnal Ekonomi: Journal of Economic*, 14(1), 28–39. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.47007/jeko.v14i01.6463>

- Rohimah, W., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *Jurnal Ekonomi Manajemen Perbankan*, Vol 5, No 1 (2023): JEMPER Januari-Juni, 30–40. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185264>
- Rohmandika, M. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Variabel Determinan Return On Asset pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *Eco-Iqtishodi: Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi Dan Keuangan Syariah*, 5(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.32670/ecoiqtishodi.v5i1.3607>
- Shalsabila, I. H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar akad kafalah pada industri keuangan syariah: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037426>
- Sufia, I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Akad Salam pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042345>
- Zahro, T. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar akad istishna' pada industri keuangan syariah: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037428>